

THE MEANING AND ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF READING CULTURE

Muborak Yakubjanovna Khakimova

Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture

e-mail: xakimova.1979@bk.ru

Abstract. In a scientific article, based on an analysis of various approaches to reading culture and information culture, their significance in the life of society, the concept of reading culture is given a definition denoting its content and essence. At the same time, the main feature is the transformation of reading into an activity that satisfies the spiritual needs of a person, in the process of this activity the formation of the psychology of reading in the mind of the subject, regulating his interaction with the outside world. publication product or sources of information, the user has a unique psychology of reading, at the same time the author, publication product, source of information, it is explained that this is a social subject who is influenced by its distribution and promotion, and that reading for one's spiritual needs is a constant activity.

Key words: reading culture, information culture, psychology of reading, publication product, sources of information, spiritual need, social subject.

1. INTRODUCTION

Information is published on a global scale with different approaches about reading culture and information culture and the formation of information culture, its importance in the life of society. All this is connected with a person's interest in various areas of knowledge and the ability to quickly find and assimilate from the flow of information what he needs and satisfy his needs.

In Uzbekistan, this issue is also given much attention at the state level. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2017 "On the creation of a commission for the development of a system of printing and distribution of book products, promotion and popularization of book reading and the culture of reading" and "Development of a system of printing and distribution of book products", adopted on September 13, 2017, about the Program comprehensive measures to increase and develop book reading and a reading culture" dated June 7, 2019 "On further improvement of the supply of book products." information and library services to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan", development and support of a reading culture in 2020-2025. When adopting the "Support Program," it was emphasized that although some work is

being done in this area, important issues related to it are being resolved. Increasing the culture of reading and reading in our society remains an urgent task.

In addition, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his work “New Strategy for the Development of Uzbekistan” wrote: “Another pressing issue that always worries me is the manners, behavior, cultural level, in a word, the education of our youth.” We are doing a lot of work in this direction. But to further improve their effectiveness, we need to pay serious attention to a number of issues. In particular, the development of reading and a reading culture among young people should always be in the center of our attention" [3. p-252]. This situation shows that library and information institutions, which are a sociocultural institution of lifelong education and a center for information support, have a special responsibility. Because in the process of obtaining printed publications and information needed by users from the library collection (with the help of a librarian or independently), the ability to use library and information resources, bibliographic knowledge, and the foundations of information culture are strengthened. are used in practice and there is a state of mutual understanding.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Review on this field shows that the activities related to the formation of a reading culture among users cannot be called conical; their knowledge of the use of library and information services is not enough. In addition, there is a noticeable inability to freely use quick and simple search methods for information sources and the information and bibliographic apparatus of the library, and a lack of competence in working with several sources of information. Most users cannot effectively use not only electronic means, but even traditional means of storing and retrieving information in a library and information institution. The exact situation of the skills and qualifications of library and information service users shows that there is a serious gap between the demand and supply of information, which in turn leads to a decrease in efficiency.

At the same time, some factors allowed in the personnel training system also influenced the formation of a reading culture in accordance with the requirements of the time. In particular, in 2012, when the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan and the Tashkent State Institute of Culture named after Abdulla Kadyri was created on the basis of the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan, the Faculty of Library and Information Management, which was previously part of the Institute of Culture, was annexed to the Tashkent University of Information Technologies. As a result of these efforts, aimed at raising the speed and quality of service to a high level through the introduction of modern information technologies into the processes of library work, these efforts deviated in an absolutely technological direction, undermining the humanitarian content of training specialists in the field of library work. field of librarianship, and a one-way approach was created. Observing the activities of graduates, it is felt that they are far behind in terms of working with users, educational impact on them, and developing a reading culture, even if they perform tasks such as programming and automation of library work well. The main reason for this is that as a result of the world's takeover by the Internet system, a false belief has arisen that “the era of the book is over.” But in recent years, strong opinions have been expressed against this approach to the book both at the level of academic science, in the practice of secondary schools, secondary specialized vocational education, and even at the UNESCO level, emphasizing the indelible and extensive cultural role of traditional books and other printed publications has passed. Starting from the 2017-2018 academic year, the educational direction “Information and Library Science” was reorganized and training began at the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan. In order to prevent one-sidedness in personnel training, based on world experience, the name of the educational direction was changed to “Library and information activities (by type of activity)” and the regulatory documents related to the educational process were changed. enhanced. Particular

attention is paid to the formation of a culture of reading and reading, which is of unsurpassed importance for the spiritual development, self-awareness and worldview of the younger generation.

Declining interest in reading, in turn, is considered one of the biggest threats to the decline in the level of literacy of the population and the sustainable development of society and the state. Therefore, many developed countries are taking strict measures to prevent this negative situation. National comprehensive programs are being developed. They provide for the adoption of systemic measures to unite the efforts of government authorities, libraries, educational institutions, subjects of education, science and entrepreneurship, civil society institutions in the field, and the media. At the same time, special attention is paid to the formation of public consciousness about the value and importance of reading, targeted support and development of a reading culture among different segments of the population, improvement of publishing activities, and the formation of a book market that fully meets the intellectual needs, spiritual and cultural needs of society. According to international experience, the adoption of such targeted programs and concepts produces positive results.

Based on this, it is necessary to comprehensively study the place and role of library and information institutions in the formation of a reading culture, firstly, between the social significance of information, information, knowledge and the level of individual reading culture; secondly, between printed publications the volume of information and a person's ability to sort, study, analyze and use it increases; thirdly, between a person's desire for information, information and knowledge and his complete satisfaction; fourthly, it is determined by the presence of inconsistencies and conflicts between society's request for library and information services and the specific capabilities of the individual in working with the information offered.

2.1. Literature Review

Since the formation of a reading culture is considered one of the social problems that determine the level of general cultural development of society, librarian scientists in our country have carried out certain work in this direction. For example, in the studies of O. Kasimova, E. A. Okhunjonov, M. A. Rakhimova, E. Yuldashev, E. Islamov, M. M. Turovov, M. Kh. Makhmudov, reading culture was considered together with general problems of librarianship.

In particular, the research of Professor E.I. Yuldashev on the topic of guiding user reading, library and children's reading put forward a number of ideas related to the creation of a national model of reading culture and the origins of its formation.

B.I. Ganieva's research work is devoted to the formation of a reading culture in children of primary school age and the problems of cooperation between families, preschool institutions, library and information institutions, and the rational organization of students' free time.

Of particular importance are A. O. Umarov's scientific and sociological analyzes of the culture of reading, its place and role in the development of society. In these studies, reading culture is analyzed as a unity of the principles of voluntariness, awareness in learning, free choice of activity, conscious motivation for improvement, principles of internal appeal, which are its important components, and is analyzed as specific driving factors of development. human development.

A. Abduazizov's research work is devoted to a sociological analysis of the formation of a reading culture among students of secondary specialized vocational educational institutions.

V. A. Borodin, scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States, on the formation and development of a personal reading culture, theoretical and methodological directions. Yu.P. Melenteeva, N.V. Zbarovskaya and L.V. Tananakina also did some work. In their work, reading culture is considered as a phenomenon, process and activity, and the activities of library and information institutions are analyzed as a necessary condition for the formation of a reading culture.

Issues of developing a reading culture among students by M.I. Gubanova, issues of orientation of children's reading in library and information institutions by V.P. Chudinova, V.D. Stelmak, N.N. Zhitomirova, V.A. Voronets, S.N. Serovars have been widely studied.

Today, when the flow of information is increasing, the virtual world is saturated with a variety of information that cultivates the spiritual thinking of all citizens, especially young people, forming in them a culture of reading and reading, turning this culture into a permanent and regular skill. becomes more important than ever.

It is known that all the great historical scientists equated and compared the book with light, the power of thought, a symbol of spirituality, a source of knowledge, a closest adviser and a true friend.

Over the two-thousand-year period of the existence of human society, many universal discoveries were made, and the invention of printing was unanimously recognized by world scientists, politicians, public figures and public organizations as a great event that made an incomparable contribution to its development. .

Although the word "mutolaa" actually means "to read", in today's information age it has a broader meaning than reading a book.

The constituent elements of a reading culture, voluntariness, the desire for conscious knowledge, freely chosen activity, conscious motivation for self-improvement are motivating factors in a person's spiritual growth.

A positive attitude towards reading and reading books has existed in Uzbek families since ancient times. Navoi, Fuzuli, Bedil, Mashrab. They read the ghazals of Uwaisi, Nadira and Abdullah Qadiri in groups, hand in hand, as a family. However, the environment typical of the reality of the 21st century requires the ability to quickly obtain what is needed from a huge flow of information, quickly analyze it and use it effectively.

Since one of the main directions of developing a reading culture is the study of the interests and needs of users, in order to determine the sources of their use, according to the results of surveys conducted in 2023 among users of the Republican Information Service. Library center, 32% of respondents (1436 people in total) get the necessary information from books, 26% from the Internet, 18% from e-books, 10% from television and radio, 4% from the workplace. Thus, most users satisfy their reading needs through books.

According to Professor E. Yuldoshev's textbook "Leading Children's Readings," reading culture is a very broad concept, and it is a skill that helps develop interest and love for books, better recognize literature, and acquire special knowledge about books and work. with them, as well as to fully use the books and requires qualifications. The culture of reading teaches the reader to fully understand literature, receive aesthetic pleasure from it, understand and evaluate the thoughts and ideas of the author. In addition, it teaches how to use books and libraries, find books on interesting or necessary issues in the information and bibliographic apparatus, and use them in reading, work and life. Choosing a book, reading it quickly, storing it carefully, organizing a personal library, the ability to recommend books and bibliographic documents read to others is part of the culture of reading. [11.p.101].

In the "Library Encyclopedia", published in the Russian Federation, "Reading culture is a set of skills and competencies necessary for the optimal organization of the reading process, achieving social goals and acquiring knowledge; A person is defined as one of the components of information culture[11]."

Reading culture is also considered as one of the typological characteristics of users. The culture of reading, together with the culture of work, life and free time, characterizes the general culture of a person, forms moral and aesthetic taste, increases the intellectual level, develops speech and generally expands the spiritual capabilities of a person.

Today, the concept of reading in scientific research is interpreted not only as the process of reading books or other publications, but also as the process of assimilation of information from various information sources.

For example, in the book by Professor A. Umarov “The Culture of Reading: Personality, Society, Development” it is stated that “Reading is a phenomenon of cognition, learning, assimilation. This is based on purposeful activity, reading and assimilation of information from the text, depending on the various needs of the social subject.” (5.p.-88)

In the mentioned literature, one can generalize ideas about reading culture and give the following definition: the concept of reading culture in a broad sense is the ability to correctly and systematically organize reading time; study in an orderly and continuous manner; is able to independently select and sort books and information; popular science or fiction, the ability to correctly think through various information, critically evaluate and draw the right conclusions; be able to find the necessary literature, information through bibliographic indicators and other sources of information; be able to carefully use books and other press publications; maintain reading hygiene, organize reading speed in accordance with the purpose; is an activity that allows you to recommend the best books and valuable information to others. Reading culture is a set of specialized knowledge, articles and experience necessary for the study of printed publications and electronic resources.

Parents have a responsibility to help their children choose books based on their age, interests and tastes, and to pay particular attention to the educational aspects of the book chosen for reading. Above all, it is important for parents to read regularly and set an example for their children. In educational institutions, namely kindergartens, junior classes, middle classes, high schools, students of academic lyceums, vocational colleges, students of higher educational institutions, the creation of a strict list of literature that must be read, taking into account their age characteristics, specialties and level control training., there is a need to create a more advanced method of stimulation.

The goal can only be achieved if the promotion of reading books in educational institutions is carried out from the point of view of language, history, religion, independence, freedom and interests of the nation.

From this point of view, the main goal should be to develop the ability to distinguish books that have a positive impact on the thinking and morality of society and the individual from books that have superficial, moral, aesthetic, and spiritual value.

3.RESEARCH RESULTS

The reading environment created in educational institutions not only has an individual impact, but also allows for the formation of a culture of mass reading with the appropriate use of mass and group influence.

In the media, especially television, people who read widely, are analytical, and can give a clear, informed opinion about each recommended piece can have a positive effect.

Otherwise, conversations between announcers and television and radio journalists who obviously have not read a given book will not have a positive impact on the formation of a reading culture.

It should be noted that the work being carried out today in the above areas does not correspond to the level of demand.

In particular, since not all parents know the rules for choosing and recommending books suitable for the age of their children, correct and expressive reading, this task mainly falls on kindergartens, schools and libraries.

The beginning of problems can be traced back to another node in the chain of problems. That is, most kindergarten teachers and school teachers are not even interested in what new books, journal

articles, and bibliographies are being published in their field or the subject they teach. Unfortunately, some of them do not even have an idea about the bibliographic index.

Most information and library institutions do not promote knowledge among readers and students about the information and bibliographic equipment they have.

Observations show that even the majority of students at higher educational institutions do not know how to correctly use information and bibliographic apparatus. As a result, the formation of a reading culture does not occur as expected, which negatively affects the growth of the general reading culture of the population. Therefore, the tasks of increasing the activity of members of society by cultivating a sense of belonging to great changes in the sphere of socio-political and cultural life require improving service to users as a collective activity of the library and information service.

Two interrelated areas - consulting users on reading and information services - constitute the main content of the library and information service.

Guiding users to read is one of the main directions of our national idea - a unique system of influencing the content of the culture of public reading with the aim of forming a perfect personality.

Information recorded through readings and symbols. is a communicative activity aimed at assimilation of information. This complex communication system includes the author-publisher-printed source)-information dissemination-dissemination-user system, and each part of it is associated with a specific area of society. The user of a library and information institution is an object of information and promotion, pre-election influence and at the same time an elected active subject.

4.CONCLUSIONS

Various sociological studies also note cases where, in terms of the purpose of attitude to information, the leaders are continuity of reading, printed publications, electronic information, and the direction of including people in the actively reading part of the population. But these indicators are variable. Continuity and continuity of reading vary depending on the free time and professional activities of a person. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight the main differentiating feature depending on the characteristics of reading.

Such a distinctive feature is the transformation of reading into an activity that satisfies the spiritual needs of a person. During this activity, the psychology of reading is formed in the subject's mind, regulating his interaction with the publication product or sources of information. Accordingly, the user is a social subject who has a unique reading psychology, who is influenced by the author, the product of the publication, the source of information, its distribution and promotion, and who carries out constant reading activity in accordance with his spiritual needs.

User research is considered as an activity aimed at improving the provision of library information services to them from a sociological, psychological and pedagogical point of view.

REFERENCES:

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the creation of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, on the promotion and promotion of book reading and reading culture. January 12, 2017.
3. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the program of measures of the commission on the development of the system of publication and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting the culture of book reading and reading. September 13, 2017.
4. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the further formation of the provision of information - library services to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan. June 7, 2019.

5. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Development strategy of new Uzbekistan. Third edition.- Tashkent: "Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2022.-440 pages.
6. Umarov A.O. Reading culture: Individual, society, development. - Tashkent: "Fan", 2004. - 194 p.
7. Ganieva B.I. Propagation of librarianship-bibliography knowledge among elementary school students.-Tashkent: 2006.-33 pages.
8. Philosophy: An encyclopedic dictionary - Tashkent: "Sharq" NMAK Chief Editorial Office, 2004. - 496 p.
9. Melentyeva Yu. P. Reading: Phenomenon, process, activity. – Moscow, Nauka, 2010. – 182 p.
10. Chudinova V.P. Development of nations of readers in different countries of the world: research, strategies, projects, practices. Moscow, Book, 2014.-344 p.
11. Abdulazizov A. Sociological analysis of the formation of reading culture.-Tashkent: "Navroz" publishing house, 2016.- 176 p.
12. Yoldoshev E. Guiding children's learning.-Tashkent: "Teacher" publishing house, 2006.-191 p.
13. Library Encyclopedia. Moscow, Pashkov House, 2012.-1335 p.